

Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CES	Centralized Energy Storage
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DES	Distributed Energy Storage
DoA	Description of Action (Annex I of the Grant Agreement)
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EV	Electric Vehicle
FO	Flexibility Operator
IIP	Integrated INVADE Platform
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OCMP	Open Capacity Management Protocol
OCPP	Open Charge Point Protocol
PLC	Power Line Communications / Carrier
PUC	Pilot Use Case
PV	Photo Voltaic
V2G	Vehicle to Grid
WP	Work Package

1 Executive summary

The goal of deliverable D.10.7 is to **verify and certify** the technical characteristics and economic gains of the INVADE platform carried out in all 5 pilots. For the INVADE project all harvested pilot-data have been analysed and optimized through the INVADE-platform. The differences between predicted and actual energy performance are measured and reported. Each pilot has analysed the improvements, and given recommendation for further improvements, when they decide “next step”. There are also climate related gains for each pilot, and these are well described in the LCA-analyses in the deliverable D.3.5.

The results show that the more complexity, the more improvements the INVADE-platform contributes with.

For the Norwegian pilot the integration of renewables and storage assets coupled with the introduction of new grid tariff structures mandates the need for use of an optimized control-plan. The INVADE platform, IIP, predicts and suggests this optimized control plan based on the harvested data from the different pilots DER`s or existing ecosystem.

In the Dutch pilot (Elaad and Greenflux), the main task is to test the use of the IIP to suggest control plans for optimizing EV-charging and reduce the grid-load (overload), and to minimize the charging cost. This is tested both on a network of public charging stations, grouped together to represent neighbourhoods, as well as on large commercial parking spaces. The improvements of using IIP, are significant. Elaad have successfully tested the bidirectional charging with good results.

In the German pilot (badenova), residential customers are equipped with PV panels, batteries and a home automation system from SMA. Here, the IIP connects to the SMA system, where this harvested data is used to return optimized control plans back to the SMA system. The results show the value of the IIP`s predictions and optimization. The German pilot also demonstrates the possibility to optimize control of the distributed energy storage (DES) assets via the IIP in a very accurate way.

In the Bulgarian pilot (Albena), the focus has been to control the energy-flow, where the resort-town has a very high energy-demand for hot water heating in its 43 hotels. The IIP platform generates optimized control plans according to electricity market prices and a prediction of DER production. The savings potential here has been demonstrated and the results shows significant cost reduction.

In the Spanish pilot, the DSO Estabanell is testing the benefits of installing a centralized energy storage (CES) at the substation level. In addition to increase the power quality, islanding test have been demonstrated successfully. The CES replaces the need of using diesel-generator backup, and hence decreases CO2 emissions.

2 Introduction

The main purpose of this document is to create a clear overview of the completed tests and demonstrations in each pilot, for a validation and certification of the achieved results/findings.

Each chapter represents one pilot, and in a structured order each pilot-owner reports the achieved optimization results of the INVADE-platformed.

Results throughout reduced cost or increased efficiency.

Tables in each chapter describes the pilot`s results both in “%-results”, and in “absolute numbers”.

Tables will also include recommendations for further improvements, after the conclusion of the project or in an adjusted next step of the optimization of the INVADE-platform.

In the last chapter, each pilot-owner evaluates his performance throughout the INVADE project versus what was stated/promised in the DoA. During the project there have been external “influencers” or technical immaturity that are the reason for changing or adjusting the pilot’s possibility for implementation of the first planned equipment/test.

3 Norway pilot: Lyse

3.1 Pilot descriptions

The Lyse pilot has investigated and demonstrated the intersection between V2H/loads/PV, power-based tariffs and energy management in private homes and buildings, and how they are combined in new business models. The pilot has also demonstrated how the Integrated INVADE System can be inter-operable with existing smart solutions. Through the pilot it has been desired to show the effect and benefit of smart management of energy-efficient components in the home in order to better utilize their own energy consumption.

From a business point of view, we believe that these kinds of services at a household level will create both customer value as downstream services in the retail market and future upstream services on a DSO level.

3.2 Pilot performances

Table 1 demonstrates the performance increase in %, from “basis” (without IIP) to INVADE stage (with IIP), and further recommendation for next stage (further developed IIP).

Metric #	Type of consumer/prosumer	Type of metric	Percentage improvement with INVADE optimization (%)	Estimated future improvement in %
1	Private households	Change energy consumption based on hourly rate	1 %	1,5 % but, it will depend on the price volatility.
2	Private households	Change to power peak-based tariffs	44% in average	46% in total if algorithms are improved
3	Private households	Utilization of own PV production (self-consumption)	17,5 % in average	19,5 % in total if algorithms are improved
4	Private households	Combination of metric 1 – 3 in combination	24 % in average savings related to energy cost in combination of metric 1 -3.	25 % in total if algorithms are improved
5	V2G test DC-charger	2- way energy Flow	10 KW reverse flow in 5seconds	Rapid use for peak-shaving

Table 1. Percentage change in performance in the Norwegian pilot

Comments:

- Due to low energy prices in Norway the improvement based on the hourly rate is limited. But the price volatility in the future could have more impact if the price varies more during the day. The price variation also varies from year to year depending on the market.
- Power peaks and the power peak tariffs tested is the most beneficial solution tested in the pilot. The percentage presented is the average peak shaving done during the day over a period.
- Utilization of own PV production is measured in improvement of self-consumption. Data collected from pilots.
- Combination of metric 1-3, measured in savings in terms of money. Complex solution where the INVADE platform really improve energy consumption.
- V2G has been tested with 10 kW reverse energy-flow for 5 seconds. First two Nissan Leaf's had a inverter breakdown, so we needed to be carefully with the third car.

Table 2 demonstrates the performance increase in absolute values, from “basis” (without IIP) to INVADE stage (with IIP), and further recommendation for next stage (further developed IIP).

Metric #	Type of consumer/prosumer	Type of metric	Baseline	INVADE optimized	Estimated future improvements in %
1	Private households	Change energy consumption based on the hourly rate	Moved from high price to low price period.	10 kWh moved to low price	0%
2	Private households	Change energy consumption based on Power based tariffs	Move high peak to low peak period	14,5 kWh moved to low peak period	1 % in total if algorithms are improved
3	Private households	Utilization of own PV production (self-consumption)	Charge battery/car when production is higher than consumed energy	From 550 kWh to 96 kWh delivered back to the grid	10 % in total if algorithms are improved
4	Private households	Combination of 1 – 3, Higher complexity	Baseline 1– 3.	1,59 € per day estimated to 580,35 € a year.	2 % in total if algorithms are improved

5	V2G – test	2- way energy Flow	One-way flow	10 KW reverse flow in 5seconds	Future AC-charger will better fit this market / need
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Table 2. Absolute change in performance in the Norwegian pilot

Comments:

- Due to low energy prices in Norway the improvement based on the hourly rate is limited even if the amount of moved hours is high. No estimated improvement in the future is possible as far as we can see.
- The total amount of kWh moved from the high peak period to the low peak period each day. This is due to a combination of EV and battery.
- Improvement of utilization. Overall improvement of 17,5 %, but it will depend on the size of the PV. The stationary battery is more relevant than the EV in this case.
- Combination of metric 1 – 3. Difficult to measure in kWh because the different metric focusing on different outputs. Result measured in € saved. Complex solution where the INVADE platform deliver a god result. The result is quite high in savings 580,35 € because of high average energy consumption in Norway - 25.000 kWh a year at households.
- V2G has been tested, and this solution is to “complicated” / immature and to expensive. Future V2G AC-chargers will replace todays V2X DC-chargers

3.3 Pilot performance compared to DOA

DoA	Delivered	Gap
The Lyse pilot will investigate and demonstrate the intersection between V2H/loads/PV, Power based tariffs and energy management, and how they can combine in new business models	Three use cases have been developed and tested. Both separately and in combination. The business model relates to savings for the customer by offering energy management as-a-service.	Objective fulfilled
Demonstrate how the Integrated INVADE platform can be inter-operable with existing smart solutions.	The existing Smart home solution and ecosystem Smartly has been fully integrated to the INVADE platform by using API.	Objective fulfilled

<p>Solutions to enable bidirectional management of customer loads. The load with the most potential and value is the battery (EV or fixed), as it can enable a two-way flow of electricity and increase the supply security to households. In addition, thermal loads like electrically heated water boilers will also be tested.</p>	<p>The connection to existing Smartly Ecosystem ensure the bidirectional management of all assets. Both fixed and EV-batteries has been tested. Thermal loads have also been tested.</p>	<p>Objective fulfilled</p>
<p>Pilot Assets from the DoA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Heater Control and floor heat control 3 zones (10 installations) • V2H control (5 installations) • Battery sets (10 installations) • PV and battery (5 installations) • PV and V2H (6 installations) 	<p>Pilot Assets delivered in the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VVB Control and heat control 3 zones (10 installations) • V2H control 1 site at the Lyse main office • EV-chargers (20 installations) • Battery sets (5 installations) • PV and battery (5 installations) • PV, battery and EV-charger (6 installations) • 50 HAN readers • PV, EV-Charger and Water Heater Control (9 installations) • Housing association with 30 kWh battery and 30 kWp PV 	<p>In lack of technology, standardisation and development within V2H it has been difficult to deliver as expected in the DoA when it comes to V2H. The pilot has a V2H setup at the Lyse HQ to do testing and validation.</p> <p>Objective partly fulfilled</p>

Table 3. Performance compared to DoA in the Norwegian pilot

4 Germany Pilot: Badenova

4.1 Pilot description

The German pilot has adopted a hybrid approach. It provides one centralised energy storage (CES) device on one hand as well as connecting already existing distributed energy storages (DES) in private households on the other hand. The business model followed within INVADE is preventing peak loads in the entire electrical grid from the perspective of the DSO 'bn-NETZE'. DSOs in Germany pay a grid usage fee to the upstream grid operator for the aggregated maximum power at the transfer points. Typically, load peaks in the grid occur in the morning, around noon or in the evening. So private households with already installed DES were invited to offer their flexibility potential to the DSO in order to contribute avoiding peaks in the grid. Further the CES was controlled in the same way.

4.2 Pilot performances

In Figure 1, the load profile for the entire electrical grid in Freiburg is shown for the year 2017 (in kWh). This means the baseline as no peak shaving was undertaken. The highest peak over the whole year is accounted by a so called 'peak tariff'. So, if the peak passes through due to an unprecise load forecast or technical problems controlling flexibility devices, all the financial advantage is lost. INVADE does not provide a load forecast for electrical grids. Therefore, it was the task of 'bn-NETZE' in its role as DSO responsible for operating the whole electrical grid.

Figure 1 indicates that the maximum peak load regarding the whole electricity grid in Freiburg is around 600 MW¹.

¹ In the figure, 15 min energy values are plotted (kWh) and the day with highest load was in May with 150 MWh. 150 MWh divided by 0.25 hours results in 600 MW peak load.

Figure 1. Load profile of the Freiburg distribution grid

Table 4 shows the performance increase in %, from “basis” (without IIP) to INVADE stage (with IIP), and further recommendation for next stage (further developed IIP).

Metric #	Type of consumer/prosumer	Type of metric	Percentage improvement with INVADE optimization [%]	Estimated future improvement in %
1	Private households – DES (6 pcs.)	Contribution to peak shaving of entire badenova grid (%)	0,001% p.a.	With 1’000 private households 0,17% p.a.
2	Central Energy Storage - CES (1 pc.)	Contribution to peak shaving of entire badenova grid (%)	0,003% p.a.	With 50 CES this size 0,17% p.a.

Table 4. Percentage change in performance in the German pilot

Comments:

- For now, ten DES are interconnected in private households in the German test site, but not all of them are connected to the same electrical grid. Six of them are located in the grid called ‘Freiburg’. The calculation above covers these six households. In addition to them comes one large CES, connected to at the end of the 850m LV-feeder.
- The potential power supply by one single battery depends on its capacity, structure of the energy demand in the household, maximal power performance of the inverter and the time range when the peak occurs. So far, we currently assume that private households can provide about 1 kW for 1 h of flexibility on

average. This means for six households a controllable flexibility of 6 kWh. The CES comes along with 20 kW for 1h; so 20 kWh.

Table 5 demonstrates the performance increase in absolute values, from “basis” (without IIP) to INVADE stage (with IIP), and further recommendation for next stage (further developed IIP).

Metric #	Type of consumer/prosumer	Type of metric	Baseline	INVADE optimized	Estimated future improvement in %
1	Private households – DES (6 pcs.)	Contribution to peak shaving of entire badenova grid (kW)	600 MW peak load minus 6 kW	544,- EUR p.a.	With 1'000 private households 90'770 EUR or 0,17% p.a.
2	Central Energy Storage - CES (1 pc.)	Contribution to peak shaving of entire badenova grid (kW)	600 MW peak load minus 20 kW	1'815,40 EUR p.a.	With 50 CES this size 90'770 EUR or 0,17% p.a.

Table 5. Absolute change in performance in the German pilot

Comments:

- Depending on the voltage level at the connecting substations, different prices are relevant. For the whole electricity grid in Freiburg, the upstream grid operator 'Netze BW' asks for 90.77 €/kW p.a. for the highest yearly peak.
- For the six already installed DESs and one CES we do not expect high cost savings due to relatively low available controllable power compared to the total power peak in the grid. However, if we predict a rapid increase of controllable DES due to further market penetration a relevant cost saving potential is evident and can be made accessible by the INVADE platform.

4.3 Pilot performance compared to DOA

In the DOA, the installation of one CES with at least 100 kWh capacity as well as the interconnection of at least ten households were promised. This target has been hit. On the other side, no performance regarding the contribution of the devices to peak shaving was assured. INVADE has gained already the maximum possible effect with this amount of connected battery storages. An increase is only possible with a higher number of participating households or respectively more large batteries like CES. In this case, an economy of scale effect can be expected, as the interconnection of distributed devices becomes more and more a standardized service with well tested hardware and

established routines. Further personal costs will decrease as it does not matter, if an employee is responsible for 100, 500 or 1000 devices when the initial installation is completed, and the system is up and running.

5 Netherland Pilot: Greenflux/Elaad

5.1 Pilot description

The goal of the Dutch pilot was to design a flexibility management system that supports the distribution grid and electricity market while coping with grid limitations, uncertainty and variability with high penetration of renewable energy, electric vehicles and an increased number of diverse smart grid actors.

5.2 Pilot performances

Table 6 demonstrates the performance increase in %, from “basis” (without IIP) to INVADE stage (with IIP), and further recommendation for next stage (further developed IIP).

Metric #	Type of consumer/prosumer	Type of metric	Percentage improvement with INVADE optimization [%]	Estimated future improvement in %
1	Private households	peak reduction using Smart Charging	59%	61% in total if algorithms are improved
2	Private households	Combined peak reduction using Smart Charging	64% average	66% in total if algorithms are improved
3	EV drivers (office charging)	Share of renewable energy used for EV charging	7% average	0-1% hard to predict future improvements

Table 6. Percentage change in performance in the Dutch pilot

Comments:

- The INVADE optimization resulted in substantial improvement especially for the households.

Table 7 demonstrates the performance increase in absolute values, from “basis” (without IIP) to INVADE stage (with IIP), and further recommendation for next stage (further developed IIP).

Metric #	Type of consumer/prosumer	Type of metric	Baseline	INVADE optimized	Estimated future improvement in %
1	Battery storage office	kW	0	Charging of max 20kW during night. Discharging during day max 45kW	5%
2	Private households	kW peakload	From 11,973 kW to below 5kW	4.4kW average	2%
3	Private households – combined optimization based on total usage	kW	75kW max	69kW max	2%
4	Public area - kW-max for grid connection	Number sessions	0 from 130.000 sessions	63558 sessions	Unknown
5	Building owners	APX spot price	€ 42,23 / MWh	(€ 42,56 / MWh	0%

Table 7. Absolute change in performance in the Dutch pilot

Comments

- Battery usage depends a lot on the capacity tariff.
- Battery consumed for own ventilation, cooling, etc. as much as 4 households per year. So far this was not considered in evaluations but has huge impact on business case
- For households combining optimization of all assets instead of single assets regarding peak load reduced the peak load during work days, but raised peak load during weekends
- Improvements share renewable energy depends a lot on available renewable energy. Impact for offices only during week days and private households mainly during week-ends.
- Impacted sessions for kW-max grid connections were a lot, but the total impact was limited to avg 40.2 minutes longer charge time which is OK.
- Optimization for building owners resulted in slightly higher spot price for energy. This is probably because they are complex/experienced actors that determine and influence on the spot price. They are outside the impact field of our INVADE pilot focus.

5.3 Pilot performance compared to DOA

DOA	Delivered	Gap
Integration of electric vehicles in the smart grid.	Fully delivered	Objective fulfilled
Implementation of Vehicle2Grid, Vehicle2Building, Vehicle2Home operations for charging, providing storage capacity or services to the grid.	V2G and V2B was tested for multiple scenario's, with both leased and shared cars.	V2H was not tested. However, the feeding back of electricity itself is the most relevant aspect of the technology, which is for that reason now named Vehicle2Anything (V2X), focussing on the direction rather than the destination of the electricity.
INVADE platform will be tested and validated with a significant number of end-users (75 EV users in NL)	40 households with EV charge stations, 8 offices with 199 semi-private EV charge stations. Large scale public 1000 public sockets with >150.000 sessions	A larger number of EV users where involved compared to the DoA. In total app. 5000 people were involved. (50 home, 400 semi private and 4550 for the public chargers)
Pilots will be implemented in real time conditions involving real consumers, prosumers and producers	40 households with EV charge stations, 8 offices with 199 semi-private EV charge stations. Large scale public: 1000 public sockets with >150.000 sessions	15 additional households and 100 additional semi private stations are used in the pilots compared to the DoA.
Pilots will be demonstrated over a 12-month period to ensure credibility and consistency of conclusions, especially considering dependency of renewable energy production on climatic conditions.	By the end of December 2019, we will have a full year of measurements. Climate effects on grid constraints have been found and effectively managed.	Objective fulfilled

Table 8. Performance compared to DoA in the Dutch pilot

6 Spanish pilot: Estabanell

6.1 Pilot description

The Spanish pilot focuses on a centralised approach. A large-scale battery of 210 kWh was installed at a secondary substation of the DSO Estabanell in order to provide flexibility through the INVADE platform to the DSO and BRP. Furthermore, the battery can act as an energy backup service for a critical site, in this case the control center room of the DSO.

Flexibility services that the battery provides to the DSO are therefore congestion management, voltage and reactive power control and controlled islanding, while for the BRP it provides self-balancing portfolio optimization.

6.2 Pilot performances

Table 9 demonstrates the performance increase in %, from “basis” (without IIP) to INVADE stage (with IIP), and further recommendation for next stage (further developed IIP).

Metric #	Type of consumer/prosumer	Type of metric	Percentage improvement with INVADE optimization	Estimated future improvement in %
1	DSO	Power losses reduction	4%	7 %
2	DSO	Capacity of the grid	Up to 1,6 %	5 %
3	BRP	Cost savings	Up to 30%	40 %
4	Consumer/critical building	Optimization Diesel Genset	144 kg CO2 emissions avoided per year	N.A.

Table 9. Percentage change in performance in the Spanish pilot

Comments:

- The power and energy losses reduction are the results of shortening the distance between generation and consumption.

- The value of increased grid capacity was calculated through simulation with Power factory, adding PV generation till reaching the value of 50% of load in the grid cables.
- The cost savings for BRP were calculated applying the economic study to MERCATOR's data of 2017.
- Climate related gains are well described in deliverable D.3.5 about the Life Cycle Analysis (LCA).

6.3 Pilot performance compared to DOA

The objective of installing a centralized storage unit of 200 kWh was met. Also, with the controlled islanding test it was proven that the battery can act as a back-up service for 2 hours for a critical building, as declared in the DOA.

However, due to the renovation of the headquarters of EPESA, the substation used in the pilot was different than the first declared in the DOA and the PV panels, that should have been initially part of the pilot, were removed. Also, for legal and regulatory issues, it was impossible to make the neighbours participate in the sharing of the storage system.

7 Bulgarian Pilot: Albena

7.1 Pilot description

The Albena pilot has been aiming at demonstrating how a disparate energy storage (both electrical and thermal) along with an increased share of renewable energy sources (RES) can contribute to reducing operational costs. For this purpose, Albena has installed a 27 kWp PV field along with a 201 kWh Li-Ion battery at one of its 5-star hotels. In addition, Albena has also installed solar thermal collectors and converted their respective water-boilers at two more hotels – one new 5-star hotel, and an older 3-star hotel to further demonstrate the applicability of such applications in legacy systems. Seeing both the financial and grid stability benefits of increasing share in controllable loads, Albena increased its hot water system conversions to 4 additional hotels, which were manually controlled, with further 4 hotels ready to be added to the IIP. This approach aims to demonstrate a large-scale installation at what has been proved to be a beneficial project direction.

7.2 Pilot performances

Table 10 shows the measurable controllable load results for the 2019 summer season during which all 6 selected hotels were operating (two INVADE controlled and four manually controlled). Exact quantification of the direct contribution of INVADE to lowering the cost per MWh is related to high measurement costs because the improvement of the local consumption is already contained within the global consumption, hence for a sufficient approximation we are instantiating a baseline for future improvements by comparing against Albena's average price per MWh. This resulted in 9.07% decrease in cost from Albena average for the two stations controlled by INVADE and 7.79% decrease in cost from Albena average due to the manual control of the four additional stations, resulting in an average 8.43% total cost decrease. This table demonstrates the performance increase in %, from "basis" (without IIP) to INVADE stage (with IIP), and further recommendation for next stage (further developed IIP).

Metric #	Type of consumer/prosumer	Type of metric	Percentage improvement with INVADE optimization [%]	Estimated future improvement in %
1	Boiler system	Savings based on reduced EUR/kWh price from Albena average	8.43%	12%
2	Boiler system	Utilization of Solar Thermal production	26.41%	33%

Table 10. Percentage cost improvement by boiler systems in the Bulgarian pilot

Further to this, the RES share in the water heating systems (as shown in Table 10) is calculated as the total share of kWhTh from the solar thermal collector compared to the total energy used for the entire season of 2019.

The battery cost savings in Table 11 are calculated using the battery state, which gives us the charge and discharge kWh. The Independent Bulgarian Energy Exchange (IBEX) day-ahead price is then used to calculate the actual cost savings. The duration period used for that calculation spans between the IIP being ready to send control signals and the end of test phase (10.09.2019 – 30.11.2019).

Table 11 demonstrates the performance increase in absolute values, from “basis” (without IIP) to INVADE stage (with IIP), and further recommendation for next stage (further developed IIP).

Metric #	Type of consumer/prosumer	Type of metric	Baseline	INVADE optimized	Estimated future improvement in %
1	Battery	Cost saved based on battery usage	€0	€24.17	5%
2	PV	Utilization of PV production	0 MWh	39.383 MWh	5%

Table 11. Percentage cost improvement by battery and PV systems

The savings from PV production shown in Table 11 are calculated based on the total produced energy since the installation of the PV field.

All estimated future improvements percentage increases for both water heating systems as well as PV and battery system are calculated based on identified occasional issues during bringing up the IIP, as well as with peripheral devices and communication, which are expected to be fixed for the next operational period.

7.3 Pilot performance compared to DOA

Albena is responsible for all activities related to pilot implementation and completion of the proposed demonstration. This includes the specification of requirements, selection of equipment, procurement of required installations, integration of new installations within existing infrastructure, integration of INVADE platform within infrastructure and existing ICT tools, engagement with end-users, pilots' implementation, data collection and analysis.

All required tasks were accomplished along with an extended large-scale demonstration of water heater controllable load systems. Concept has been proved, key implementation and exploitation findings have been discovered and workflows within the Bulgarian energy and tax law have been created.

The energy produced due to increased RES share (both PV and thermal), was observed to significantly reduce the consumer cost.

8 Common findings from INVADE and recommendations

The pilots in INVADE have in different ways explored the potential of energy storage at various levels in the distribution grid. The results harvested have produced insight of high specific and general value. All the use cases have shown that energy storage in various forms can yield substantial benefits. The results presented above show that energy storage can make a significant difference within the existing European regime. However, analyses of the results for each pilot indicate that the benefits can be higher provided that national policies and regulations are changed. Margins are either reduced or potential energy gains are inhibited because of regulatory barriers. It serves to the credit of pilot owners such as Badenova that has managed to establish viable business cases based on storage and acute forecasting within the existing German regulations. Like other INVADE pilots, Badenova shows very well how INVADE can make a substantial economic difference and societal impact by reducing peaks and optimize the local demand with local supply. The Lyse pilot shows how new tariffs can leverage the case of energy storage and good control. A regulatory framework with capacity oriented or Time of Use tariffs create incentives for investment in distributed storage facilities. As shown, the individual economic benefits can become substantial. The Lyse case is thus a prime example on how regulatory changes may pave the way for investment in storage that ultimately provides an economic benefit, but at the same time increases load control that can generate effects far into the central energy market. Moreover, some critical mass is needed. Economy of scale is required for most cases tested and the future potential highlighted by pilot owners typically hinges on this.

Smart charging has proven to be a viable option for Charge Point Operators (CPOs) and EV drivers alike. Currently the marginal costs of Smart Charging are lower than that of stationary batteries and other buffer technologies. The Greenflux/ElaadNL pilots have demonstrated how it can be applied to create an impact. The effect of the optimized control plans from INVADE has proven that the number of charging points can be increased even if the physical limit in ampere is not enough to allow concurrent charging on all points. By applying user volunteered information, the total load can be optimized to avoid system breakdown, while the user experience for the EV driver or the CPO is not jeopardized. In fact, this INVADE pilot in the Netherlands has shown that smart charging can increase the service level since the charging of more EVs can be managed and utilization of parking space can improve. The test of scalability in this pilot provides

technical insight that shows that “economy of scale” is technically possible. Critical mass can be established by syndicating many different resources, locally or distributed, that creates a significant economic impact and a more even load profile. The societal effects that can be derived from this should be obvious. The uptake of EVs that need to charge can increase accordingly. Hence, a significant barrier for a smooth transition from fossil-based to fossil-free transportation can be removed. The Elaad/Greenflux pilot has also shown how self-consumption rate for locally generated energy can increase by better control of energy consumption due to charging.

The case of Albena has shown how a mix of thermal and electric energy production on site, together with a stationary battery and management of thermal storage can help improve the energy profiles of multiple co-located hotels. Early investments where standardization of control across multiple hotels were realized economy of scale have been catered for. Moreover, it shows how the foundations for a future energy community can be established where trade in flexibility within the community is possible by means of INVADE. Currently, manual operations can still challenge the use of more automated approaches enabled by INVADE. However, as more hotels are insourced the complexity is going to increase, and the resulting complexity is likely to outmatch the manual alternative, automated and full integrated systems like INVADE will become more profitable.

Critical mass is also essential to build a good business case for the Spanish pilot. However, the existing and potential benefits established, provided regulatory changes are significant. Based on the collective results it can be established that INVADE and the different forms of storage tested can be make a positive difference to fulfil the ambitions specified in the DOA.

It has been proven that V2G/B is still a very immature technology. Procurement of two-way chargers have been prone to delays, faulty information from suppliers and high costs. The experience gathered so far is that V2G/B is currently oversold by vendors in the market. The V2G/B business case is not obvious due to the current high cost of functional hardware. However, the combination of V2G/B with other services as pointed out by the Dutch pilot shows that V2G/B could still defend investments and be part of a full suite of storage and control systems that could be effectively operated by INVADE.

Currently, there are some basic insight that have transpired from the overall effort in WP10:

- Optimization and control with the aid of INVADE and storage do make a difference, in increased energy performance and load management as well as better uptake of locally generated energy from renewable sources.
- There is a need for “critical mass” to harvest economic benefits. There is no absolute threshold for when that critical limit can be reached. Analysis of the pilots show that this can vary. However, it means that the more units connected, the better more pronounced the benefits of INVADE and storage become.
- Centralized storage would be preferable to distributed storage at this stage. This is because of small margins and the need for “critical” mass to make a difference. Decentralized storage would require more investments in reliable communication and increased management and maintenance.
- Associated with the above, the more complex and bigger the operation undertaken the more relevant INVADE becomes. Increased complexity rules out other options that can be used for simple “one-of-a-kind” systems that can be operated by means of local controllers or partly manually.
- As can be seen from the pilots, INVADE produces a better yield if the aggregator part of the FO is included. One example is Badenova. Sole focus on the low-end energy service part to reduce peaks and save costs for the individual is less attractive for the INVADE platform.
- The current regulatory framework has shaped the pilots but liberalizing the position of storage in the grid and further improvement of forecasting and optimization can increase the value potential.
- Benefits, especially for prosumer services, are highly dependent on their tariff structure. In this sense, scenarios with flat tariffs can offer limited benefits, while scenarios with ToU tariffs or with subscribed power can be more interesting to implement INVADE solutions.